

PARAMETRIC STUDY ON PLASMA ARC CUTTING OF ALUMINIUM-6061

¹Jaksan D. Patel, ²Kalpesh D.Maniya, ³Vikram V. Patel, ⁴Virang Patel.

¹Asso. Prof. Mech. Engg., ²Asso. Prof. Mech. Engg., ³Asst. Prof. Mech. Eng. ⁴PG Student

^{1,3}Merchant Engineering College, Basna, Mehsana, India, ²C.K.Pithwala College of Engineering & Technology, Surat, ⁴PG Student Merchant Engineering Collage, Basna, Mehsana, India.

Abstract: In the last 40 years, there is terrific research in machining and development in technology. With an increase in the race in market and to make high accuracy nowadays the nonconventional machining have become a lifeline of any industry. Plasma arc cutting is a non-conventional thermal cutting process that makes use of a constricted jet of high-temperature plasma gas to melt and separate the metal. Plasma arc machining is most important non-conventional machining technique because of high accuracy, finishing, high speed, and capability to machine any hard surface. The existing work purposes to review the consequences of process parameters in air plasma arc cutting on Al-6061 material. The 5 mm thick Aluminium alloy 6061 plates use as work material which is used in Bus and Truck frames and chassis, high-pressure gas cylinders, structure application, Marine Frames, automobile frames, Furniture, and fabrication work. Pressure cutting current and speed were designated as process parameters. The trial cut experiments were performed to find out the range of each process parameter for a detailed experiment. Based on the range attained by exploratory experiments, three levels of Pressure current and speed were selected within this range for detailed experimentation. The cut quality parameters like material removal rate (MRR), top kerf width (KT), bottom kerf width (KB) and bevel angle (BV) are measured and analysed. The main effect plots were created to find out the effect of input parameters on response parameters at each level. The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was performed to find out the percentage contribution of each process parameter on performance characteristics. Minitab 20 software was used to generate main effect plots, s/n ratio, and analysis of variance table.

Keywords: Plasma Arc Welding, ANOVA, MRR, KT, KB, BV

1. Introduction

Thermal manufacturing and non-conventional machining method used for processing different electrical conducting materials like stainless steel, carbon steel, aluminum, cast iron, and non-ferrous metals are known as Plasma Arc Cutting. Plasma is a gas that conducts electricity. Ionization generates the development of free electrons and positive ions in the middle of gas atoms. This results in the formation of a plasma, which is a gas that is electrically conductive and susceptible to conducting electricity.

PAC working process and mechanism are shown in figure 1.1. In this method, the electrode acts as a negative charge, whereas the workpiece functions as a positive charge. Cutting gases including n₂, O₂, air, and others are used in the presence of the electrode. High voltage charges are put onto the electrode. Cutting gas gets ionized and transformed into plasma, and creates an arc. Heavy gas similar to Argon, Neon is used as a shielding gas to protect arc from atmospheric conditions. A concentrated electrical arc melts the material over in this approach, which is then completed by a high-temperature plasma beam. It is possible to cut any conductive material. Plasma cutting current from 20amp to 1000amp and cut plate are inert gas is 5mm to 160mm thicknesses.

Plasma gases are compressed air, nitrogen, oxygen, or argon/hydrogen to cut high alloy steels and mild steel, Aluminium, copper, brass, and other metals and alloys.

Figure-1:working principle of plasma arc cutting

The basic principle is that the arc between the electrode and the workpiece is constrained by using a fine-bore copper nozzle. The temperature and velocity of the plasma emitted from the nozzle are increased as a result. Plasma has a temperature of 20,000°C and a velocity that would be faster than the speed of sound. When used for cutting, the plasma gas flow is increased, producing a more penetrating plasma jet that can cut through the material as liquid metal is discharged in the efflux plasma.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review establishes the scope of the current study and serves as a guide for doing the analysis. The literature review is essential for gathering information regarding the dissertation project. A distinct study on plasma arc cutting procedures for improved surface finish using parametric analysis is included in the literature, and the effect of cutting speed, arc current, gas pressure, and other so many parameters affect surface finish and material removal rate.

A Review on Optimization of Plasma Arc Cutting Parameters Using Taguchi Method for EN19 By 1) Kunal S. Panchal, 2) Dr. Mitesh J. Mungla2.et, (2020). PAC is one of the most important non-conventional machining methods in this study, and it is also rated as a difficult technology when compared to related technologies such as laser cutting and oxy-fuel. The optimization of PAC has been an open research topic for a long time. In this study, the optimization of plasma arc cutting parameters is discussed. Taguchi method was used to achieve the best results and achieve the aim. The proper orthogonal array is chosen based on the number of components and their levels, as well as the amount of experimentation required. The following are the outcomes of the experiment and analysis: 1) PAC is one of the most commonly used for that is capable of manufacturing complex parts. 2) Cutting speed, gas pressure, arc current, arc gap, gas flow rate, and arc voltage

are the most appropriate process parameters from the above-described studies. 3) Material removal rate, surface roughness, and kerf will be the response variables in an experiment with process parameters such as cutting speed, gas pressure, arc current, and arc gap. 4) Plasma arc cutting is assisted process as well as an optimization technique. In PAC some new research scopes like Improvements in modeling techniques take prepared opportunity to have plasma arc cutting and improve the performance of Plasma Arc Cutting.

Plasma arc cutting optimization parameters for aluminum alloy with two thickness by using Taguchi method By 1) B. Abdunnasser, 2) R. Bhuvnesh. Et (2016) the work aims to consider the surface roughness of the projects that reduce the material including the material removal rate during the plasma arc cutting process. The specimens constructed of aluminum alloy 1100 were cut to use a plasma arc cutter machine model PS-100 with parameters selected. The results indicate that the current and cutting speed are the most significant parameters. The experiment was carried out on specimens with thicknesses of 3 mm and 6 mm. The experiment was carried out using L9 orthogonal arrays and the Taguchi standard approach. Process parameters included Arc current, cutting speed, and arc gap. The weight of the specimens before and after cutting was used to calculate the material removal rate (MRR). The current Material Removal Rate was significant, according to the results of the experiment.

Application of Signal-to-Noise (S/N) Ratios and ANOVA for the Prediction of Optimal Designs of Multiple Performance Characteristics 1) B. Naga Raju, 2) Ch. Maheswara Rao, 3) B.B. Ashok Kumar (2020). In the present work, aluminium metal matrix composite is taken as the workpiece and the experiments were Carried out using CNC-wire electric discharge machine. For the specified process parameters of Pon, Poff, and Ip at three distinct levels, the experiments were planned according to Taguchi's standard L27 OA. The output properties are optimized using Taguchi's Signal-to-Noise ratios and ANOVA. The best response designs were predicted and proven to be more accurate and sufficient. According to the results of the analysis of variance, Pon and Poff are the most important influencing parameters for MRR and Ra, respectively.

Experimental Study and Optimisation of Mrr In CNC Plasma ARC Cutting 1) Gurwinder Singh, 2) Shalom Akhai (2015). The major objectives of this practical experiment are to find the best possible settings and operating parameters for a CNC plasma arc machine to achieve fast work, i.e. maximum material removal rate. This study shows how the Taguchi method may be used to optimize the machining parameters of a CNC Plasma Arc Cutting Machine. It has been demonstrated that by employing the optimal amount of parameters, the Material Removal Rate in the CNC Plasma Arc Cutting process may be significantly improved. Based on the study conducted on MILD STEEL. Cutting Speed is the only element that has a significant effect, while Kerfs and standoff distance are less effective. For the same current value, steam as a plasma gas will generate more energy than other gases. Cutting speed is critical for achieving maximum material removal rates. The MRR increases as the cutting speed increases.

Advance Manufacturing Processes Review Part VI: Plasma ARC Machining (PAM) 1) Swapnil Umredkar, 2) Vallabh Bhoyar (2019).

In today's metal cutting technology, good dimensional accuracy and high-quality cut surfaces are required without further operations. This paper focuses on current research and results produced using the plasma arc machining process based on specific processing parameters, experiments, and various optimization strategies that have been employed for plasma machining process optimization. This analysis aims to describe how to evaluate processing parameters such as scanning speed, cutting power, cutting height, and plasma gas pressure. Gas pressure, cutting speed, arc voltage, arc current, standoff distance, and gas flow rate are all process parameters that affect the quality characteristics of plasma cuts including bevel angle, heat affected zone (HAZ), kerf generated, and surface finish. PAM and its assisted processes, and also optimization strategies, have opened up new study areas in PAM. Modeling technique developments have opened up new study possibilities in PAM and improved the process' performance.

TAGUCHI METHODOLOGY

Taguchi method was developed by Dr. Genichi Taguchi born in 1924 in Japan. This is a Fractional Factorial design method based on orthogonal array. This method also requires a large number of experiments when the process parameters increase. This technique is used to find best set of values of controllable factors to type the design less sensitive with variation of noise, which means that Taguchi make a design more robust.

Figure-2: Flow Chart for Taguchi Methodology

3. EXPERIMENTATION

3.1 Material

For current study, 120 x 50 x 5 mm Aluminium Alloy 6061 plate was used as workpiece which has a medium to high strength heat-treatable alloy. ALUMINIUM 6061 is one of the most commonly used grades aluminum

grades in the world. The aluminum sheet, aluminum plate, aluminum bar, or aluminum angle, 6061 is the choice for wide range of applications. . It has very good corrosion resistance and very good weldability and reduced strength in the welded zone. It has medium fatigue strength. It has good cold formability, it allows design of brighter, more efficient and durable product structures.

Composition	Al	Mg	Cu	Cr	Si	Fe
Percentage	95.8-98.6	0.80-1.20	0.15-0.40	0.04-0.35	0.40-0.80	0.0-0.70

Table-1:Composition of AA 6061

3.2 Machine

Parameter	Range
Power voltage (v)	Single phase 220v ±15%
Rated input power (kva)	6.6
No load voltage (v)	230
Rated input current (A)	30
Rated output voltage (v)	96
Duty cycle	60%
Pilot arc model	HF oscillating
Burner inter diameter (mm)	1
Pressure of air (bar)	4-5
Thickness	1-12
Weight (kg)	9
Size (mm)	371 x 153 x 232

The experiment was conduct using a Quality CUT 40 Air Plasma Cutting Machine. Machine has four main components. (1) Power supply unit, (2) Air supplyunit , (3) Trolley unit, (4) Plasma torch head assembly unit. In this machine torch mounted on the automatic travel trolley. Cutting speed is change by regulator knob.

Table-3: Air Plasma Cutting Machine Specifications for CUT 40

4. Experiment runs

Response surface methodology (RSM) is a collection of mathematical and statistical techniques for empirical model building. An experiment is a series of tests, called runs, in which changes are made in the input variables in order to identify the reasons for changes in the output response. The most frequently used second-order designs are the central composite and the Box–Behnken designs. Three process parameter (current, pressure, and Speed) was selected for this study. From the result of trail cut, the three level of current (30, 35, 40 A), Speed (0.99, 1.05, 1.11 m/min) and pressure (4, 4.5, 5 bar) was select. MRR was measure by weighting equipment and Top kerf width, Bottom kerf width and Bevel angle was measure by measuring microscope

SR NO	PRESSURE (bar)	CURRENT (amp)	SPEED (m/min)	T1 (sec)	MRR (mm ³ /min)	KT (mm)	KB (mm)	BV (deg)
1	4.5	30	0.99	22.78	1170.61	3.64	2.91	4.17
2	4.5	35	1.05	13.40	2321.72	3.78	2.64	5.82
3	4.5	40	1.11	8.25	3771.04	3.68	2.68	5.71
4	5.0	30	1.05	14.64	1214.32	3.62	2.31	6.78
5	5.0	35	1.11	9.65	3223.94	3.35	2.22	6.16
6	5.0	40	0.99	10.38	1712.69	3.57	3.04	2.74
7	5.5	30	1.11	6.61	1680.95	3.05	1.38	9.53
8	5.5	35	0.99	14.71	1359.61	2.90	2.12	4.46
9	5.5	40	1.05	11.66	2477.60	2.72	1.33	7.40

Table-4.1:Observation Table

5. Result And Discussion

5.1 Taguchi orthogonal array design MRR

5.1.1 Main effect plot for MRR

➤ Taguchi Analysis: MRR versus Pressure, Current, Speed

Table 5.1 Material Remove RateResponse for Means

Level	Pressure	Current	Speed
1	2421	1355	1414
2	2050	2302	2005
3	1839	2654	2892
Delta	582	1298	1478
Rank	3	2	1

Figure 5.1 Main Effects Plot for Material Remove Rate

From the main effects plot in Figure 5.1 for MRR, it is observed that the pressure increase blowing of gas is producing a cooling effect and reducing the plasma arc temperature. And next with an increased current MRR is an increased, showing that the current increases electrical energy input so in this case increasing the plasma arc temperature. And increasing speed the cut area covered increased and allowing the plasma arc to cut over longer distances and MRR to increase.

5.1.2 S/N ratio plots for the MRR

Level	Pressure	Current	Speed
1	66.74	62.52	62.90
2	65.51	66.72	65.90
3	65.02	68.03	68.74
Delta	1.72	5.51	5.83
Rank	3	2	1

5.2Response Table For S/N Ratio

Fig. 5.2 Main effect plots for S/N ratio

Fig. 5.2 shows the S/N ratio plots for the MRR. For this experiment, a higher-the-better S/N

ratio has been used. From the response table and S/N ratio, by using MINITAB-20 software. We can estimate that P1, C3, And S3 is the optimal parameter combination for MRR. Current = 40A, gas pressure = 4.5 bar and cutting speed is 1.11 mm³/min.

5.1.3 Analysis of variance for MRR

Table 5.3 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for MRR response.

Source	DF	Seq SS	Contribution	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Pressure	1	507626	7.50%	507626	507626	5.55	0.065
Current	1	2529088	37.36%	2529088	2529088	27.66	0.003
Speed	1	3275278	48.38%	3275278	3275278	35.82	0.002
Error	5	457232	6.75%	457232	91446		
Total	8	6769224	100.00%				

The percentage effect of all factors on replies is the most crucial information that can be acquired here. Model terms with a P value of less than 0.0500 are significant. Cutting Speed and Current are important model parameters in this situation. The model terms are not important if the value is bigger than 0.1000. It is noted that the most significant parameter for material removal rate is found in all parameters. The percentage contribution of Pressure Current and Speed on MRR are 7.50%, 37.36% and 48.38% respectively.

5.2 Taguchi orthogonal array design top kerf width

5.2.1 Main effect plot for top kerf width

- **Taguchi Analysis: KT versus Pressure, Current, Speed**

Level	Pressure	Current	Speed
1	3.700	3.437	3.370
2	3.513	3.343	3.373
3	2.890	3.323	3.360
Delta	0.810	0.113	0.013
Rank	1	2	3

Table 5.4 Top Kerf Width (KT) Response for Means

Figure 5.3 Main Effects Plot (data means) for Top Kerf Width (KT)

From the main effects plot in Figure 5.3 for KT, It has been discovered that pressure has the greatest impact on top kerf width; as pressure rises, the blowing of gas is producing a cooling effect and reduces the plasma arc

temperature. And with an increase in current, heat energy is increased. The temperature of the arc is higher and it penetrates thrust metal rather than spread in sideways. Arc is remaining and the heat of the arc lesser time consumed with speed increasing. As the exposure to heat in the plasma arc at a given point reduces hence kerf width reduces.

5.2.2 S/N ratio plots for the KT

5.5 Response Table For S/N Ratio

Level	Pressure	Current	Speed
1	-11.363	-10.694	-10.508
2	-10.909	-10.433	-10.472
3	-9.208	-10.354	-10.501
Delta	2.154	0.340	0.036
Rank	1	2	3

Figure 5.4 Effects of various factors on S/N Ratio of KT

Fig. 5.4 shows the S/N ratio plots for the KT. For this experiment, the Smaller-is-better S/N ratio has been used. from the response table and S/N ratio, by using MINITAB-20 software We can estimate that P1, C1, And S1 is the optimal parameter combination for MRR. Current = 30 A, pressure = 4.5 bar and cutting speed is 0.99 mm3/min.

5.2.3 Analysis of Variance for Top Kerf

Width (KT)

Pressure is the most significant parameter for Top Kerf width, according to Table 5.6. Pressure Current and Speed contribute 83.47%, 1.97%, and 0.01%, correspondingly, to Top Kerf Width.

Table 5.6 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for Top Kerf width response

Source	DF	Seq SS	Contribution	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Pressure	1	0.96802	83.47%	0.968017	0.968017	28.69	0.003
Current	1	0.02282	1.97%	0.022817	0.022817	0.68	0.448
Speed	1	0.00015	0.01%	0.000150	0.000150	0.00	0.949
Error	5	0.16871	14.55%	0.168706	0.033741		
Total	8	1.15969	100.00%				

5.3 Taguchi orthogonal array design bottom kerf width

5.3.1 Main effect plot for bottom kerf width

Level	Pressure	Current	Speed
1	2.743	2.200	2.690
2	2.523	2.327	2.093
3	1.610	2.350	2.093
Delta	1.133	0.150	0.597
Rank	1	3	2

Taguchi Analysis: KB versus pressure, current, speed

Table 5.7 Bottom Kerf Width (KB) Response for Means

Figure 5.5 Main Effects Plot (data means) for Bottom Kerf Width (KB)

From the main effects plot in Figure 5.5 for KB, It has been determined that pressure has the greatest impact on bottom kerf width, blowing metal, and splitting the cut at the bottom kerf width. And next with an increased current it's observed that KB increases, the increasing current because increasing arc temperature leads to greater melting at bottom of the workpiece.

With increased speed, there is less time for the plasma arc to make contact with the material.

Level	Pressure	Current	Speed
1	-8.758	-6.449	-8.487
2	-7.952	-7.295	-6.060
3	-3.934	-6.899	-6.096
Delta	4.824	0.846	2.427
Rank	1	3	2

5.3.2 S/N ratio plots for the KB

Fig-5.6: Effect of various factor on s/n ratio of KT

Table-5.8: Response Table For S/N ratio

Fig. 5.6 shows the S/N ratio plots for the KB. The smaller-is-better S/N ratio was applied in this experiment. Using MINITAB-20 software, we extract several interactions from the answer table as well as S/N ratios. Looking at the graph. We can estimate that P1 C2 S1 is the optimal parameter combination for KB. Current = 35 A, gas pressure = 4.5 bar and Cutting speed = 0.99 mm³/min.

5.3.2 Analysis of Variance for Bottom Kerf Width (KB)

Table 5.9 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for KB

Source	DF	Seq SS	Contribution	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Pressure	1	1.92667	64.11%	1.92667	1.92667	18.85	0.007
Current	1	0.03375	1.12%	0.03375	0.03375	0.33	0.590
Speed	1	0.53402	17.77%	0.53402	0.53402	5.23	0.071
Error	5	0.51092	17.00%	0.51092	0.10218		
Total	8	3.00536	100.00%				

Pressure is the most significant parameter for Bottom Kerf width, according to Table-5.9. Pressure Current and Speed each contribute 64.11%, 1.12%, and 17.77% to KB, accordingly.

5.4 Taguchi orthogonal array design Bevel Angle

5.4.1 Main Effect plot for Bevel Angle

Level	Pressure	Current	Speed
1	5.233	6.827	3.790
2	5.227	5.480	6.667
3	7.130	5.283	7.133
Delta	1.903	1.543	3.343
Rank	2	3	1

➤ **Taguchi Analysis: BV versus Pressure, Current, Speed**
 Table 5.10 Bevel Angle (BV) Response for Means

Figure 5.7 Main Effects Plot (data means) for Bevel Angle (BV)

With increasing pressure, the blowing effect blows a greater amount of molten material from the top forwards to the bottom of the cut then increases the BV. And with increasing current arc temperature increasing. It's reduced is the side spread of energy and increased penetration allowing straight cut with reduced BV. And with increasing speed the exposure to plasma arc at a given point is less. This causes unequal heating and melting at the top and bottom of the workpiece generating increasing BV.

5.4.2 S/N ratio plots for the Bevel Angle

Table 5.11 RESPONSE TABLE FOR S/N RATIO

Level	Pressure	Current	Speed
1	-14.28	-16.20	-11.38
2	-13.72	-14.69	-16.44
3	-16.65	-13.76	-16.84
Delta	2.93	2.45	5.45
Rank	2	3	1

Figure 5.8 Effects of various factors on S/N Ratio of BV

Fig.5.8 shows the S/N ratio plots for the BV. For this experiment, Smaller-is-better S/N ratio has been used. We get some interactions from the response table and S/N ratios using MINITAB-20 software. We may conclude that P3 C1 S3 is the optimal parameter combination for BV. Cutting speed = 1.11 mm³/min, gas pressure = 5.5 bar and current = 30 A

5.4.3 Analysis of Variance for Bevel Angle (BV)

Table 5.12 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for Bevel angle response.

Source	DF	Seq SS	Contribution	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
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Pressure	1	5.369	17.21%	5.396	5.396	4.80	0.080
Current	1	3.573	11.40%	3.573	3.573	3.18	0.135
Speed	1	16.767	53.48%	16.767	16.767	14.93	0.012
Error	5	5.616	17.91%	5.616	1.123		
Total	8	31.351	100.00%				

From Table-5.12, it is observed that Speed show most significant parameter for Bevel Angle. The percentage contribution of Pressure Current and Speed on KB are 17.21%, 11.40% and 53.48% respectively.

5.5 CONCLUSION

1. Based on some preliminary testing, it was discovered that aluminium alloy 6061 with a thickness of 5 mm can cut currents ranging from 30 to 40 amps. A current of 30A is Capable to melt the 5mm thick metal. The plasma arc cutting machines employed in this project have a maximum current range of 40A. A range of 4.5bar to 5.5bar and 0.99 mm³/min to 1.1mm³/min can also be set for pressure and speed, accordingly. For a good quality cut, all parameter has an appropriate value.
2. Main effect plots of different factor on the MRR, if the increasing value of pressure MRR is decreasing. By increasing the value of current and speed MRR is increased. And the optimal combination of the cutting process parameters is obtained as pressure 5.5bar, current 40A and speed is 1.1m/min and ANOVA analysis it concludes that speed contributes highest 48.38% on MRR. And pressure 7.50% and current 37.36%.
3. Main effect plots of Top kerf width if the increasing value of pressure KT is decreased By increasing value of current and slight decreases. While for speed slight decreases. While for speed slight decrease and then increases kt. An optimal combination of the cutting process parameters is obtained as pressure 4.5bar, current 30A and speed is 0.99m/min and pressure contribute is highest 83.47% Top Kerf Width.
4. For Bottom Kerf width pressure is the most significant parameter when pressure is increased decreases bottom kerf width. While current is increase with KB is increase and speed is increase with a decrease KB. And the optimal combination of the cutting process parameters is obtained as pressure 4.5bar, current 35A and speed is 0.99m/min And pressure contribution is highest at 64.11% and current 1.2%, and speed 17.77%.
5. For Bevel Angle, the speed and pressure are most significant than cutting current. If the increased value of pressure bevel angle increases and current value increased bevel angle decrease and speed increase BV increases. And the optimal combination of the cutting process parameters is obtained as pressure 5.5bar, current 30A and speed is 1.1m/min. and ANOVA analysis conclude that speed contributes the highest 53.48% on Beval angle. Pressure 17.21% and current 11.40%.

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